

Human Resource Management: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: This article aims to find how human resource management based on literature review from previous research from several countries around the world. This article uses search and review methods, where the review process began with a search engine, Google scholar, to search articles with keywords. The authors found the scope of the reviewed articles was still limited so it needs to be followed up related to human resource management. Result of the review show that human resource can run optimally if they apply good management. The research about this topic is limited and this article is a literature review, so further research needs to be done related to human resource management and to include other data collection methods including interview and questionnaire. The theoretical benefit of this article is to add knowledge about human resource management and the practical benefit is as an information for further research.

KEYWORDS: Education, Human Resource, Management

INTRODUCTION

The era of globalization promises a future full of challenges and competition. The era of the universe, which is not limited by time and place, makes human resources who always want to improve their quality so that they are not left behind by others (Çalışkan, 2010). According to Flippo and French human resource management is the recruitment, selection, development, maintenance, and use of human resource to the provision of compensation to achieve individual and organizational goals. (Margaretha, 2019).

The most strategic asset for a nation and state is human resource. Because the progress of a nation and state is not only based on the availability of natural resource, but is also determined by the quality of human resources. The quality of human resource is determined by the quality and level of education.

Management is an important part of life which at the same time distinguishes humans from other creatures. The focus of management is a group of people coordinating interrelated activities by using resources to achieve organizational goals. The managerial process consists of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling. This process takes place in management functions which include human resources and organization. (Ramini santika, 2020)

Human are born in organizations, educated by organizations, and almost all humans spend their life working for organizations. Every organization in general really needs human resources because for organizations, human resources are the most valuable asset they have. Likewise in educational institutions, human resource management is very important to implement. Without human resource management, an organization will generally find it difficult to achieve its goals. The role of human resource management in educational institutions is certainly very contributing in helping to improve the quality of education, because quality education comes from the people who manage education itself are quality human resource as well. (Akilah, 2018)

The quality of human resources in the implementation of education is the spirit of the school. This soft property drives the curriculum system as well as other facilities and infrastructure so that educational services can be provided. The teacher in the learning process functions as a motivator and facilitator for student to develop their potential optimally by utilizing all available learning facilities and a conducive learning system. (Wijaya, 2009). There are issues related to human resource management in schools. To be able to answer these issues, a literature review will be conducted on.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The discussion on human resource management is that humans are the most important element in all organizations, the success of the organization in achieving its goals and various goals and its ability to face various challenges, both external and internal is largely determined by the ability to manage human resources as precisely as possible. (Akilah, 2018)

Human resources are the most important assets in an organization, both for-profit and non-profit organizations. It is a source that drives, guides, maintains, and develops organizations in the various demand of society and the times. Human resources are seen as a very decisive process in organizational development (Öztürk, 2016). The importance of human resources in an organization demands that every organization get qualified and productive employees to run the organization (Baharun, Hefniy, Silviani, Maarif, & Wibowo, 2021)

The process of making a decision about what positions inside the firm to fill and how to fill them. It is also the process of identifying current and future human resource needs for an organization to achieve its goals as well as forecasting a firm's future demand and supply. This function serves as a link to the overall strategic plan of an organization. Human resource planning is a continuous process that works on both long-term and short term.(Obeidat, 2012)

Human resource management that is carried out properly will make a significant contribution in achieving the goals of the organization or company. Human resource management is tasked with studying and developing ways in which people can be effectively integrated into various organizations in order to achieve their goals. The task of human resource management revolves around efforts to manage the human element with all its potential as effectively as possible so that satisfied and satisfying human resources can be obtained for the organization.(Rokhmaniyah, 2017)

The quality of human resources is determined by the quality and level of education. The low quality of education causes the quality of human resources to be low, the higher the level of education, the higher the quality of human resources. This affects the way of thinking, reasoning, insight, breadth and depth of knowledge. The progress of Asian countries such as Singapore, Korea, Taiwan, Hong Kong, China, and Malaysia is largely determined by the quality of human resources.. (Yusutria, 2017)

Human resource management is part or management science that focuses its attention on regulating the role of human resources in the activities of an organization or institution. Human resources need to be managed properly, so that they can play a role in accordance with their function, especially in educational institutions (Owenbiugie & Ekhaize, 2020). Referring to educational institutions, the human resources in question are educators and education staff. Mulyasa explained that the purpose of human resource management is to effectively and efficiently utilize educational staff to achieve optimal results but still in pleasant conditions.(Werdiningsih, 2021)

Human resource development is a planned effort of an organization to improve the knowledge, skills and capabilities of existing human resources. The development of human resource management is important due to changes in humans, technology, work, and organization. Development is an activity to maintain and improve teacher competence to achieve organizational effectiveness. According to Flipppo, development is a process of:

1. Training to improve skills and knowledge to do certain jobs.
2. Education related to the expansion of general knowledge and background.(Ramini santika, 2020)

Human resource management in educational institutions is all activities related to acknowledging the importance of educators and education personnel in schools that are vital human resources, who contribute or contribute to school goals and utilize functions and activities that ensure that human resources are utilized optimally. Effective and one for the benefit of individuals schools and society.(Akilah, 2018)

The essence of educational human resource management is how to increase the participation and contribution of educational human resources optimally in the process of transforming educational services in schools. The process of managing educational human resources in order to achieve these goals is traditionally carried out through four integral processes, that is: the selection process, education and training, evaluation and remuneration, and development. The integrity of the four processes and the depth of each process are generally perceived to have a high correlation with the degree of human resources in schools.(Wijaya, 2009)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This literature focuses on management human resource.

A. Search and Review Methods

The review process began with a search engine, Google Scholar, to search for articles with keyword “management human resource”. The search ranged from 2005-2021 and identified a total of 150 studies and articles. The criteria for inclusion in this study are as follows:

- a. Qualitative results from management human resource
- b. Research carried out in the world
- c. The research uses English
- d. Dissertations and these are excluded

Steps in the literature review of each of the management human resource include:

Step 1: Formulate the Problem

- Choose a topic that fits the issue and interest
- The problem must be written completely and accurately

Step 2: Look for Literature

- Look for literature relevant to research
- Get an overview of the research topic
- Research sources are very helpful if supported by knowledge of the topic being studied
- These sources provide an overview/summary of the previous research

Step 3: Evaluate Data

- Look at any contribution to the topic discussed
- Search and find the right data source as needed to support research
- It can be in the form of qualitative data, quantitative data or data derived from a combination of both

Step 4: Analysis and Interpretation

Step 5: Discuss and find and summarize literature

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section reports the main findings reviewed from several articles the author has read. The analysis selected most of the articles based on the benefits and management of human resource. The articles that have been reviewed are research conducted in several countries in the world. The table describes the results of the literature review conducted by the author. Research has been carried out in several schools and universities.

Table: Management Human Resource

Author and Year	Title	Country	Method	Results
Çalışkan, E. N. (2010)	The impact of strategic human resource	Turkish	Qualitative	Human resources are an important source of competitive advantage. Human resource
Author and Year	Title	Country	Method	Results
	management on organizational performance			management practices have a positive effect on company performance

Obeidat, B.Y. (2012)	The relationship between human resource information system (HRIS) functions and human resource management (HRM) functionalities	Jordan	Quantitative	Human resources information system are considered to be one of the most important element that affect the activates of human resource department.
Öztürk, S. (2016)	Human resources managemen in educational faculties of state universities in Turkey	Turkey	Qualitative	Human resources management is shaped according to the administrative cultures of faculties, personal characteristics, democratic attitudes and understandings of the administrators, and consciousness and awareness of the administered people and therefore significant differences exist between the faculties; and human resources management culture has not developed at all in many faculties.
Rokhmaniyah, R. (2017)	Manajemen sumber daya manusia untuk mencapai pendidikan yang berkualitas di sekolah dasar	Indonesia	Qualitative	Human resource planning is based on real situations and conditions in schools, labor recruitment activities as well as recruitment in companies through selection and interviews.
Yusutria, M. (2017)	Profesionalisme guru dalam meningkatkan kualitas sumber daya manusia	Indonesia	Literature review	The progress of a nation is determined by the quality of human resources rather than the wealth of natural resources. To improve the quality of human resources, quality education is needed.
Akilah, F. (2018)	Peran Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Dalam Lembaga Pendidikan	Indonesia	Literature review	Human resource management is one of the fields of general management which includes aspects of planning, organizing, implementing, and controlling.
Author and Year	Title	Country	Method	Results
				To achieve the optimal meaning of human resources, management with clear goals is needed.
Margaretha, E. (2019)	Implementasi manajemen sumber daya manusia dalam meningkatkan kualitas pendidikan di PAUD Pelangi bunda kota metro	Indonesia	Qualitative	The recruitment and selection process is carried out by means of publication, development is carried out by attending training, maintenance is carried out by maintaining good cooperation.

Owenbiugie, R. O., & Ekhaise, R. E. (2019)	Human Resource Management Motivational Strategies for Enhancing Business Educators' Job Performance in Tertiary Institutions in Edo and Delta States, Nigeria.	Nigeria	Qualitative and Quantitative	It was recommended that workers should be sufficiently empowered to enhance higher performance and more productive. This will also go a long way to reduce attrition rate, the use of verbal praise, allowing workers' personal development should be given priority attention by management to enhance higher productivity, and management should redesign tasks/jobs from time to time so as to enhance motivation, job satisfaction, commitment to reduce absenteeism and turnover, among others.
Ramini Santika, N. W. (2020)	Manajemen sumber daya manusia dalam pendidikan karakter	Indonesia	Literature review	Management is the science and art of managing the process of utilizing human resources and other resources effectively to achieve a certain goal.
Baharun, H., Hefniy, H., dkk. (2021)	Knowledge sharing management: strategy for improving quality of human resource	Indonesia	Qualitative	The strategy to improve the quality of human resources through knowledge sharing is carried out through utilizing materials, talk space, knowledge sharing culture, benchmarking best practices.
Werdiningsih, W. (2021)	Manajemen sumber daya manusia dalam	Indonesia	Literature review	Some thing that can be done are by conducting online learning training, forming a team that
Author and Year	Title	Country	Method	Results
	meningkatkan kompetensi guru melaksanakan pembelajaran daring			focuses on assisting teachers in preparing online learning and conducting ongoing academic supervision.

Research studies on human resource management that have been carried out in various countries. The table above shows that research studies on human resource management have been carried out in schools and universities. Based on the results of the literature review and a review of the sources obtained, the analysis shows that human resources management is an important component in a program within the organization. Human resource management is essentially an activity to achieve success in facing challenges through policies, practices, and systems that influence the behavior, attitudes, and performance of employees within the organization. The quality of education cannot be separated from the existence of human resources. It is undeniable that good quality education from good human resources as well. In addition to human resources good management also greatly affects the quality of education. So, to get good human resources, management must be carried out optimally.(Margaretha, 2019)

Human resources are a source of knowledge, skills, and abilities that are accumulated in an organization. Schools that face various competitive challenges related to globalization, increasing profitability through growth, intellectual capital, technology, and continuous change. In facing these challenges, schools must develop intangible advantages or competitive advantages. In order to create a sustainable competitive advantage, schools need the support of school principals and quality school employees. Therefore, the principal must be able to develop his competence, innovation, and creativity, and act as an agent of change so that he can see the functions of human resources as a source of competitive advantage in schools.(Wijaya, 2009)

CONCLUSION

This article aims to see how human resource management is managed based on the literature review objectives from previous research. Most of the results of the literature review show that it is difficult to obtain literature related to human resource management. Human resource management is one of the fields of general management which includes aspects of planning, organizing, implementing, and controlling.

In conclusion, the authors of the present paper are convinced that the study of human resource is fruitful step for advancement of human resource information and its practices. Having such an advanced understanding will also make it possible to develop human resource apps more comprehensible.

The authors are aware that the present study is not without limitations. Because of the chosen research procedure, this study may not have enabled complete coverage of all the articles in the field of human resource. Yet, it seems reasonable to assume that the review process covered a large share of published studies available. Finally, this paper proposes some future research directions, which are not exhaustive but represent initial.

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